

Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means Clustering Algorithm on Level Set Method for Noisy Images

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Abstract— In this paper, Adaptive fuzzy c-means (AFCM) was used to generate an initial contour curve which overcomes leaking at the boundary during the curve propagation. Firstly, AFCM algorithm computes the fuzzy membership values for each pixel. On the basis of AFCM the edge indicator function was redefined. Using the edge indicator function the segmentation of medical images which are added with salt and pepper noise was performed to extract the regions of interest for further processing. The results of the above process of segmentation showed a considerable improvement in the evolution of the level set function.

Keywords: Image segmentation; AFCM; level set method; images.

I. INTRODUCTION

Image segmentation is plays an important role in the field of image understanding, image analysis, pattern identification. The foremost essential goal of the segmentation process is to partition an image into regions that are homogeneous (uniform) with respect to one or more self characteristics and features. Clustering has long been a popular approach to un tested pattern recognition. The fuzzy c-means (FCM)[1] algorithm, as a typical clustering algorithm, has been utilized in a wide range of engineering and scientific disciplines such as medicine imaging, bioinformatics, pattern recognition, and data mining. Given a data $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subset R^p$, the original FCM algorithm partitions X into c fuzzy subsets by minimizing the following objective function

$$J_m(U, V) = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{k=1}^n u_{ik}^m \|x_i - v_i\|^2 \dots \dots \dots (1) \text{Where } c$$

is the number of cluster and selected as a specified Value in the paper, n the number of data points, u_k , the member of x_k in class i , satisfying $\sum_{i=1}^c u_{ik}$, m the quantity controlling clustering fuzziness and v is set of control cluster centers or a prototypes ($v_i \in R^p$). The function J_m is minimized by the famous alternate iterative algorithm. Since the original FCM uses the squared-norm to measure inner product with an appropriate 'kernel' function, one

similarity between prototypes and data points, it can only be effective in clustering 'spherical' clusters. And many algorithms are resulting from the FCM in order to cluster more general dataset. Most of those algorithms are realized by replacing the squared-norm in Eq (1) the object function of FCM with other similarity trial (metric) [1-2].

The level set method is [4-7] based on geometric deformable model, which translate the problem of evolution 2-D (3-D) close curve(surface) into the evolution of level set function in the space with higher dimension to obtain the advantage in managing the topology changing of the shape. The level set method has had great success in computer graphics and vision. Also, it has been widely used in medical imaging for segmentation and shape recovery [8-9]. However, there are some insufficiencies in traditional level set method.

Firstly, as using the local marginal information of the image, it is difficult to obtain a perfect result when there's a fuzzy or discrete boundary in the region, and the leaking problem is inescapably appeared; Secondly, solving the partial differential equation of the level set function requires numerical processing at each point of the image domain which is a time consuming process; Finally, if the initial evolution contour is given at will, the iteration time would increase greatly, too large or too small contour will cause the convergence of evolution curve to the contour of object

incorrectly. Therefore, some modification has been proposed to improve the speed function of curve evolution [10-12].

II. ADAPTIVE FUZZY C-MEANS CLUSTERING (AFCM):

The standard fuzzy c-means objective function for partitioning $\{x_k\}_{k=1}^N$ into c clusters is given by

$$J(U, V) = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik}^p \|x_k - v_i\|^2 \text{----- (3.1)}$$

Where $\{x_k\}_{k=1}^N$ the feature vectors for each pixel are, $\{v_i\}_{i=1}^c$ are the prototypes of the clusters and the array $[u_{ik}] = U$ represents a partition matrix, namely

$$\sum_{i=1}^c u_{ik} = 1 \mid 0 \leq u_{ik} \leq 1, \forall k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \text{----- (3.2)}$$

and $0 \leq \sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik} \leq N \text{----- (3.3)}$

The parameter p is a weighting exponent on each fuzzy membership and determines the amount of fuzziness of the resulting classification. The FCM objective function is minimized when the high membership values are assigned to pixels whose intensities are close to the centroid of their particular class, and low membership values are assigned when the pixel data is far from the centroid.

The constrained optimization could be solved using one Lagrange multiplier

$$F_m = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik}^p \|x_k - v_i\|^2 + \lambda (1 - \sum_{i=1}^c u_{ik}) \text{----- (3.4)}$$

Where λ denotes a Lagrange multiplier. The derivative of

F_m w.r.t u_{ik} was computed and the result was set to zero, for $p > 1$

$$\frac{\partial F_m}{\partial u_{ik}} = p u_{ik}^{p-1} \|x_k - v_i\|^2 - \lambda \text{----- (3.5)}$$

$$u_{ik} = \left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^{\frac{1}{m-1}} \frac{1}{\|x_k - v_i\|^{\frac{2}{m-1}}} \text{----- (3.6)}$$

The identity constraint $\sum_{j=1}^c u_{jk} = 1 \forall k$ was taken into

account, $\left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^{\frac{1}{m-1}} \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{1}{\|x_k - v_j\|^{\frac{2}{m-1}}} = 1 \text{----- (3.7)}$

This allows us to determine the Lagrange multiplier λ

$$\left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^{\frac{1}{m-1}} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^c \frac{1}{\|x_k - v_j\|^{\frac{2}{m-1}}}} \text{----- (3.8)}$$

The zero-gradient condition for the membership estimator can be rewritten as

$$u_{ik} = \left[\frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^c \left(\frac{\|x_k - v_i\|^{\frac{2}{p-1}}}{\|x_k - v_j\|^{\frac{2}{p-1}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{N}}} \right]^{\frac{1}{N}} \text{----- (3.9)}$$

Where N is adaptive variable Parameter.

As no constraints, the computations of the prototypes were straightforward, The minimum of J was computed with respect to v_i , and yielded the following equation

$$\nabla_{v_i} J = 0 \text{----- (3.10)}$$

The detailed solution depends on the distance function. In the case of the Euclidean distance, this leads to the expression:

$$2 \sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik}^p (x_k - v_i) = 0 \text{----- (3.11)}$$

So the following could be immediately obtained

$$v_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik}^p x_k}{\sum_{k=1}^N u_{ik}^p} \text{----- (3.12)}$$

The AFCM algorithm for segmenting the image into different clusters can be summarized in the following steps:

AFCM Algorithm:

Step 1: Select initial class prototype $\{v_i\}_{i=1}^c$.

Step 2: Update all memberships u_{ik} with Eq. (3.9).

Step 3: Obtain the prototype of clusters in the forms of weighted average with Eq. (3.12).

Step 4: Repeat step 2-3 till termination. The termination criterion is $\|V_{new} - V_{old}\| \leq \epsilon$.

Where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm. V is the vector of cluster centers ϵ is a small number that can be set by user (here $\epsilon = 0.01$).

III. THE MODIFICATION TO THE LEVEL SET METHOD

The level set method was invented by Osher and Sethian [4] to hold the topology changes of curves. A simple representation is that when a surface intersects with the zero plane to give the curve when this surface changes, and the curve changes according with the surface changes. The heart of the level set method is the implicit representation of the interface. To get an equation describing varying of the curve or the front with time, we started with the zero level set function at the front as follows:

$$\phi(x, y, t) = 0, \text{ if } (x, y) \in 1 \dots\dots\dots (4.1)$$

Then computed its derivative which is also equal to zero

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} = 0 \dots\dots\dots (4.2)$$

Converting the terms to the dot product form of the gradient vector and the x and y derivatives vector, we go

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} \right) \bullet \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \right) = 0 \dots\dots\dots (4.3)$$

Multiplying and dividing by $\nabla \phi$ and taking the other part to be F the equation was gotten as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + F |\nabla \phi| = 0 \dots\dots\dots (4.4)$$

According to literature [9][12], an energy function was defined:

$$E(\phi) = \mu E_{int}(\phi) + E_{ext}(\phi) \dots\dots\dots (4.5)$$

Where $E_{ext}(\phi)$ was called the external energy, and $E_{int}(\phi)$ was called the internal energy. These energy functions were represented as:

$$E_{int}(\phi) = \int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{2} (\nabla \phi - 1)^2 dx dy \dots\dots\dots (4.6)$$

$$E_{ext}(\phi) = \lambda L_g(\phi) + \nu A_g(\phi) \dots\dots\dots (4.7)$$

$$L_g = \int_{\Omega} g \delta(\phi) |\nabla \phi| dx dy \dots\dots\dots (4.8)$$

$$A_g = \int_{\Omega} g H(-\phi) dx dy \dots\dots\dots (4.9)$$

$$g = \frac{1}{1 + |\nabla G_{\sigma} * I|} \dots\dots\dots (4.10)$$

Where $L_g(\phi)$ was the length of zero level curve of ϕ ; and A_g could be viewed as the weighted area; I was the image and g was the edge indicator function. In conventional(traditional) level set methods, it is numerically necessary to keep the evolving level set function close to a signed distance function[13][14]. Re-initialization, a technique for occasionally re-initializing the level set function to a signed distance function during the evolution,

has been extensively used as a numerical remedy for maintaining stable curve evolution and ensuring desirable results.

From the practical viewpoints, the re-initialization process can be quite convoluted, expensive, and has subtle side effects [15]. In order to overcome the problem, Li et al [8] proposed a new variational level set formulation, which could be easily implemented by simple finite difference scheme, without the need of re-initialization. The details of the algorithm are in the literature [8]. However, because only the gradient information was imposed in the edge indicator function, Li's method has a little effect on the presence of fuzzy boundaries.

In the paper, a innovative method was proposed to modify the algorithm. The original image was threshold into some sub images by Adaptive threshold. The threshold boundary of each sub image was weighted by α , the edge indicator function was redefined:

$$g' = g + \alpha \cdot g_2 \dots\dots\dots (4.11)$$

Where $g_2 = \frac{1}{1 + |\nabla G_{\sigma} * I_1|}$

I_1 Was the image after threshold. The iterative equation of level set functional was:

$$\frac{(\phi^{n+1} - \phi^n)}{\tau} = \mu \left[\Delta \phi - \text{div} \left(\frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} \right) \right] + \lambda \delta(\phi) \text{div} \left(g \frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} \right) + \nu g' \delta(\phi) \dots\dots\dots (4.12)$$

Taking $g' = g + \alpha \cdot g_2$ into 4.12

$$\phi^{n+1} = \phi^n + \tau \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mu \left[\nabla \phi - \text{div} \left(\frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} \right) \right] \lambda \delta(\phi) \text{div} \left(g \frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} \right) \\ + \nu g \delta(\phi) + \alpha \left[\lambda \delta(\phi) \text{div} \left(g_2 \frac{\nabla \phi}{|\nabla \phi|} \right) + \nu g_2(\phi) \right] \end{array} \right\} \dots\dots\dots (4.13)$$

Where $\alpha \in [0,1]$. When processing images of weak boundary or low contrasts, a bigger α was taken; otherwise, a smaller α was taken.

IV. THE GENERATION OF INITIAL CONTOUR CURVE

On the basis of AFCM clustering in brain MR image segmentation, the over segmentation usually exists. In this paper, the result of AFCM was used as initial contour curve, and the automated initialization of deformation model was finished. For all the pixels in each cluster i.e. white matter, if 4 neighborhoods included the heterogeneous pixel, the pixel was regarded as candidate boundary point. So the algorithm of curve tracing [18] was proposed. The exterior

boundary of the cluster was tracked in the candidate boundary points. Finally, the closed curve was obtained. The candidate boundary points, whose Euclidean distances to the origin coordinates were shortest, were chosen as initiation points of curve tracing. The steps of image segmentation with adapted level set method were as follows:

Step1. Set the number of clusters, then the original image was processed with FCM, and calculate the g_2 .

Step2. Choose one cluster, evaluate the inside area with $-\rho$ and the outside area with $+\rho$, ρ is a plus constant. The boundary of the area is set to 0. The region of interest is defined initial contour.

Step3. Minimize the overall energy functional with 4.13 formula.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The segmentation of image takes an important branch in the surgery navigation and tumor radiotherapy. However, due to medical imaging characteristics, the low contrast and fuzzy boundary is usually occurred in the images. In the experiment, the samples of images are taken from internet as shown in Figure i. The approximate contour of white matter was got by AFCM algorithm shown in Figure ii.

Figure i are the original test images ,

Figure ii are the results of AFCM clustering , to extracting the white matter.

Figure iii are the results of final contour with proposed salt &pepper noise method.

The snooping of regions else appear as a result of the in excess of segmentation. The initial evolution curve was obtained by the automated initialization. Because of the improved edge indicator function, the curve regularly evolved to the object boundaries in the process of evolution. The result established that the improved algorithm can extract the contour of object enhanced.

With the enhanced method, the curve was successfully evolved to the hollow white matter boundaries, but only to the approximately white matter boundaries with Li's method. At the same time, because the curve has been converged to the narrow region the object boundaries extraction could not be implemented with Li's method. But the enhanced method solved this problem better. On the similar computing proposal, under a 3.0GHz Pentium iv PC with 1 GB RAM on board, the average processing time of improved method was 9.6s, and that was 30.3s with Li's method. The evolution time was greatly reduced.

VI. DISCUSSIONS

The need of the re-initialization is completely eliminated by the proposal of Chunming Li, for pure partial differential equation driven level set methods, the variational level set methods. It can be easily implemented by using simple finite difference method and is computationally more efficient than the traditional level set methods. But, in this algorithm, the edge indicator has little effect on the low contrast image. So it is hard to obtain a perfect result when the region has a discrete boundary. Meanwhile, the initial contour of evolution needs to be determined by manual, and it has the shortcomings of time-consuming and user intervention.

In this paper, we projected a new method to transform the algorithm. The original image was partitioned with AFCM, and the controlled action of the edge indicator function was increased. The result of AFCM segmentation was used to obtain the initial contour of level set method. With the new edge indicator function, results of image segmentation showed that the improved algorithm can exactly extract the corresponding region of interest. Under the same computing proposal, the average time cost was lower. Alternatively the AFCM clustering is sensitive to noise; some redundant boundaries were appeared in the candidates. Consecutively to solve this problem, the algorithm of curve tracing was proposed.

Figure i Original Test Image Figure ii Afcm segmented with salt & pepper Figure iii Final contour with proposed method

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the results of the mixture of AFCM with the level set methods could be used for the segmentation of low contrast images and medical images. The method has the advantages of no reinitialization, automation, and reducing the number of iterations. The validity of new algorithm was verified in the process of exacting details of images. In the future research, noise was added in images prior information on the object boundary extraction with level set method, such as boundary, shape, and size, would be further analyzed. At the same time, the performance of image segmentation algorithms would be improved by modernization of classic velocity of level set method.

REFERENCES

- [1] J.C.Bezdek ,Pattern Recognition with Fuzzy Objective Function Algorithms,Plenum Press ,New York,1981.
- [2] K.L.Wu,M.S.Yang,Alternative c-means clustering algorithms,Pattern Recognition vol.35,pp.2267-2278,2002.
- [3] L.Zhang,W.D.Zhou,L.C.Jiao.Kernel clustering algorithm, Chinese J. Computers,vol25(6),pp.587-590,2002(in chinese).
- [4] Osher S, Sethian J.A,Fronts propagating with curvature dependent speed: algorithm's based on the Hamilton-Jacobi formulation.Journal of Computational Physics,1988,pp.12-49.
- [5] Malladi,R,Sethain,J., and Vemuri,B., Shape modelling with front propagation: A level set approach.IEEE Trans.Pattern Anal.Mach.Intell, 1995, pp.158-175.
- [6] Staib,L., Zeng,X., Schultz,R., and Duncan,J., Shape constraints in deformablemodels.Handbook of Medical Imaging,Bankman,I.,ed., 2000,pp.147-157.
- [7] Leventon,M., Faugeraus,O., Grimson,W., and Wells,W..Level set based segmentation with intensity and curvature priors.Workshop on Mathematical Methods in Biomedical Image Analysis Proceedings,2000,pp.4-11.
- [8] Paragios , Deriche R,Geodesic active contours and level sets for the detection and tracking of moving objects. IEEE Transaction on pattern Analsis and Machine In telligence,2000,pp.266-280.
- [9] Vese L A,Chan T F, A multiphase level set frame wor for image segmentation using the mumford and shah model. International Journal of Computer Vision,2002,pp.271-293.
- [10] Shi Yanggang,Karl W C, Real-time tracking usin g level set, IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition,2005,pp,34-42
- [11] Li Chunming, xu Chengyang,Gui Changfeng,et al, Level set evolution without re-initialization:a new varitional formulation.IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and pattern Recognition,2005,pp.430-436.
- [12] Sethain, J., Level set Methods and Fast Marching Methods.Cambridge University Press 1999
- [13] Dunn, J.C., A fuzzy relative of the ISODATA process and its use in detecting compact well-separated Clusters.J.Cybern., 1973,pp.32-57.
- [14] Bezedek,J., A convergence ththeorem for the fuzzy ISODATA clustering algorithms. IEEE Trans.Pattern Anal.Mach.Intell., 1980,pp 78-82.
- [15] S.Osher and R.Fedkiw, level set methods and Dynamic implicit surfaces,Sp[ringer,2002,pp.112-113.

- [16] Li Chunming, xu Chengyang,Gui Changfeng,et al, Level set evolution without re-initialization:a new varitional formulation.IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and pattern Recognition,2005,pp.430-436.
- [17] Bezedek,J., A convergence theorem for the fuzzy ISODATA clustering algorithms. IEEE Trans.Pattern Anal.Mach.Intell., 1980,pp 78-82.
- [18] McInerney T, Terzopoulos D,Deformable models in medical image analysis: a survey.Medical Analysis,1996,pp.91-108.
- [19] Tara.saikumar, S.Venkatesh, Md.Ameen uddin, "Adaptive FCM Clustering algorithm on Level Set method for Biomertics",in NC-ISKE,MREC,Hyderabad.

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